

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

INTERESTS OF OLDER PRESCHOOL CHILDREN IN CHOOSING A PROFESSION

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Abstract

Career guidance in early education is an important aspect in the upbringing of a child and the development of skills that will be necessary for a successful career and self-knowledge. In this regard, the study of professional orientation in play activities with the help of pedagogical design is an urgent issue in the process of educating older preschoolers. The purpose of the study is to study the aspects of the use of pedagogical design tools during the play activities of older preschoolers with early career guidance. Methods of analysis, comparison, generalization are used in this work. As a result of the study, it was possible to study aspects of project activity in the game forms of early career guidance work with older students of preschool educational institutions. The periodization of professional orientation for Ginsberg was also studied. In this paper, the early period of the child's career guidance "fantasy" is analyzed and thoroughly investigated. The study also presents variants of play activities in modern preschool education as elements of early career guidance work with older preschoolers. The scientific study highlighted the tools of gaming activity during the early career guidance of older preschoolers, namely the use of the Laptop project, augmented reality and artificial intelligence systems, as well as the MeTycoon game, which includes video materials and information about professions. The results of this scientific work can be used by researchers and scientists studying the use of pedagogical design in the process of professional orientation through games, as well as educators of preschool educational institutions who are engaged in early career guidance activities.

Keywords: children, early career guidance, preschool organization, specialty

An adult preschooler is an individual who is able to respond to himself at the age of 5-6 years. Individuals of this age are those in a period where they can get feedback through dialogue, imitate, repeat an action, observe a fantasy phenomenon. Today, adult preschoolers have a very high level of play tendency and cognition. Because those at this stage are considered to be those who are able to pass the concept of "I", self-respect, self-responsiveness. For example, a child has cognitive, creative, structural characteristics, and health. The child can constantly maintain a relationship with the environment on an equal footing. It is necessary to teach Early Career Guidance work at a time when the child is able to develop and fully recognize the types of professions. We must divide their interests into areas.

- Physical specialties;
- Social Professions;
- Technical specialties;
- Natural science specialties;
- Planetary professions;
- Media specialties;
- Маманд specialties;
- Radio-electronic specialties;
- Agricultural specialties;
- Medical mammoths;
- Military specialties;
- Defense line specialties;
- National specialties;
- Laboratory research specialties;

- Historical and humanitarian specialties;
- Linguistic specialties;
- Service management specialties;
- Underwater world specialties;
- Environmental specialties;
- Scientific research specialties;
- Zoological specialties;
- Botanical specialties;
- Logistics specialties.

And how and in what format do we explain the types of professions? Before that, there were "specialty corners" in preschool organizations. And its species and qualitative composition remained only in the image of the wall or in the corners. And it is clear that it will not work if the child does not try it on a daily basis and does not feel it in practice. Therefore, it is necessary to create not only visual corners for the child, but also labyrinths, including equipment. In this regard, I am making my own author's proposal.

The qualitative composition of the labyrinth is made of gel rubber and divided into special parts. Of these, the section of specialties, consisting of 8 qualitative parts, is indicated. The children of the group go to their desired specialty and perform their work using toy tools in a free format, wearing a special uniform as a specialist. Thus, by observing children from the outside, you can see which child is most concentrated in which profession. To do this, I conducted a research test for children of the private kindergarten "Alma". 8 types of professions are as follows:

- Doctor;

- Teacher;
- Hairdresser;
- Seller;
- Police;
- Fireman;
- Cook;
- Builder.

Through this list of professions, the child was able to concentrate on his desired profession in a free maze. Of the 25 children in the group, 13 are boys and 12 are girls. The most popular professions were" police "6," doctor "5," firefighter "3," Teacher "3," Builder "2," hairdresser "3," cook "2," seller " 1 child.

Scientists J. R. Curry and A. Milsom [1] are convinced that the approach to career development should be individual and take into account the characteristics and needs of each student. In addition, according to the researchers, it is important to take into account the personal values, hobbies, preferences and strengths of each child when choosing a career path and developing an appropriate plan. J. R. Curry and A. Milsom argue that an individual approach will help students find satisfaction from their work and achieve success in their careers. It is necessary to thoroughly investigate this issue when educating and selecting professional guidelines for older preschoolers.

According to researchers S. K. Abildina, S. H. Medieva, R. B. Asilbava, as well as their colleague K. T. Analbekova [2], the lexeme "design" has an interdisciplinary character, therefore the concept of pedagogical design can have different interpretations. In addition, scientists draw attention to the fact that in the field of cognitive theory there are several directions, such as behaviorism, cognitivism, connectivism and constructivism, which relate to the learning process, and therefore, they include the concepts of learning through reaction to various stimuli, experience reorganization to give meaning to external stimuli, creating systems and decision-making, knowledge formation through joint creativity and creation of conditions for independent active cognition. As a result, the concept of "pedagogical design", as stated in the study of S. K. Abildina, S. H. Medieva, R. B. Asilbava, as well as their colleague K. T. Analbekova, is a complex of innovative approaches and teaching methods created to improve the efficiency and convenience of professional pedagogical practice. It is

necessary to investigate the issue of pedagogical design from the side of early career guidance of older preschoolers with the help of play activities.

Early career guidance includes various activities that help children get acquainted with different professions and learn about various aspects of professional activity. In the process of early career guidance, such methods as games, contests, excursions, master classes, conversations with representatives of different professions and other forms of work are used. They help children gain the necessary knowledge about various professions, skills and abilities that may be useful to them in the future when choosing a profession.

It is important to remember that the process of career guidance is long and gradual, and children can change their interests and preferences over time. Therefore, it is important to create conditions for constant acquaintance with various professions and discussions of career opportunities so that the child can make an informed choice in the future.

As a result of this study, various aspects of early career guidance were studied when using game formats that can positively influence the choice of a future career. Also, as a result, it was possible to study the influence of games on the development of skills and competencies necessary for their future professional activity in older preschool children. The work investigated the tools of pedagogical design in early career guidance, the use of projects, augmented reality and artificial intelligence systems, as well as the game "MeTycoon" as innovative methods that are useful for older preschool children for self-determination. The study managed to study the main aspects of the periodization of career

guidance for Ginsberg, as well as to highlight the earliest period of children's professional orientation "fantasy". The paper presents the tools of early career guidance, which have a positive impact on the future professional self-determination of the child. In this paper, the pedagogical design tool "Laptop" is studied, as well

as its main tasks and functions in career guidance work with older preschool children. Researchers who will study the issues of pedagogical design in the early professional orientation of older preschool children are recommended to pay special attention to the field of digital models of career guidance work.

<p>Concept idea of the project</p>	<p>Promotion of early professional orientation of preschool children by means of an additional general educational general development program developed on the principles of integration of several subprograms (projects):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Using the modular principle of program implementation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> virtual Module "For children – about mechanical engineering"; module "Special design"; <p>76</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> "Ural model" module; "TV-Start-UP" module; the "DIA-PRO" module. <p>The content of each of the mini-projects of the program reveals and supplements information about the profession of adults in the Southern Urals – mechanical engineer.</p> <p>The content of the virtual module "For children – about machine building" is aimed at familiarizing preschool children with adult professions on Southern Urals".</p> <p>The content of the mini-project "Special Design" is aimed at attracting children to modeling, technological design and production of workwear for machine builders.</p> <p>The content of the mini-project "Ural model" includes familiarization of children with the technological process of manufacturing models of machines produced by the machine-building plant of Chelyabinsk.</p> <p>The content of the mini-project "TV-Start-UP" is directed- It is aimed at attracting children to create fascinating TV shows about the life of machine-building plant workers.</p> <p>The content of the mini-project "DIA-PROFI" is aimed at developing a system for monitoring the achievements of a child in familiarizing himself with adult professions, manifested in his daily activity in the cultural practices of childhood (play, cognitive research, visual, constructive, creative)</p>
<p>The novelty of the project</p>	<p>The novelty of the project is to use the educational opportunities of the pedagogical process within the framework of integrating the content of all educational fields, types of cultural practices and forms of pedagogical events to solve the problems of early career guidance for preschool children.</p> <p>The implementation of the project has its own characteristics:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Using the modular principle of program implementation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> virtual Module: "For children – about mechanical engineering"; module "Special design"; module "Ural model"; module "TV-Start-UP"; the "DIA-PRO" module. <p>77</p> <p>All educational modules are interconnected,</p>

	<p>this ensures the integration of various types of cognitive, constructive , model, creative activities necessary for children to achieve a positive result and achieve the goal of the program. The modular principle will significantly increase the number of children included in the project, the productivity and effectiveness of the development of the program.</p> <p>2. The use of design and research educational technologies related to the search for new forms, constructive solutions, non-standard use of materials when creating models of machines, tractors, machine tools, tools for the professional activity of machine builders, as well as workwear items.</p> <p>3. Organization of various forms of educational events aimed at identifying personal achievements of children (skill contest , presentation contest of clothing collections, competition of author models of cars and tractors, fashion week , etc.).</p> <p>4. Active involvement of children in the process communications: preparation of reports, design and work with interviews, compilation of information programs about the activities of the machine-building plant, its people and achievements.</p> <p>5. Network inclusion of partners, residents, kindergarten students in the implementation of the project, whose activities involve the inclusion of children in such project activities.</p> <p>6. The use of low-formalized and highly formalized diagnostic procedures in assessing the level of knowledge of children about adult professions</p>
Goals and objectives of the project	<p>The purpose of the project: to provide conditions for early career guidance of preschool children by means of a project integrating the following areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – familiarization of children with adult professions on In the Southern Urals: with the profession of a machine builder, designer of workwear, journalist, designer; <p>78</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – creation of a developing career guidance environment in the preschool educational institution (toys, play equipment for industrial-themed role-playing games, exhibitions of productive activities, etc.); - creation of a digital educational space to familiarize preschool children with professions of the Southern Urals (virtual museums, travel, computer games, etc.); – creation of a monitoring system for familiarizing children with adult professions. <p>Tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – development of value orientation for engineering and working professions of adults in the Southern Urals; – formation of children's knowledge about the modern production process at a machine -building plant; about art and fashion design; about the features of a journalist's work; about the creative work of adults at a toy factory; – formation of children's competencies in

	<p>research, cognitive, constructive-modeling and design activities;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – training in classical techniques of working with paper, cardboard, fabrics, modern technologies in the field of art of technical modeling and fashion design (graphics, mixed media, applique, batik, collage, etc.); – creating conditions for free experimentation with artistic materials, tools and techniques; – development of diagnostic tools to identify the formation of children's ideas about adult professions
Domain of subject knowledge	<p>The content of the project includes the integration of five educational areas of the Federal State Educational Standard UP to.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Cognitive development. 2. Speech development. 3. Artistic and aesthetic development. 4. Social and communicative development. 5. Physical development
Description of the image-calling result	<p>The project provides for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – the formation of competencies in the field of independent cognitive activity; – formation of children's ideas about different professions, <p>79</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – children's understanding of the importance of adult professional activity for society, – development of interest in adult professions on Southern Urals; – formation of a respectful attitude towards a working person, – increasing the prestige of engineering and working professions; – formation of teamwork skills, – formation of public speaking skills; – development of the ability to solve non-traditional technical and design-model tasks. – development of diagnostic competence of teachers in assessing children's knowledge about the professional activities of adults
Project roadmap	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Creation of a creative group for the design of a management project. 2. Development of Regulations on the innovative activity of teachers of preschool educational institutions (for each preschool participant of the project). 3. Creation of a model of motivation of creative pedagogical work of teachers participating in the project. 4. Creation of material and technical conditions in the DOW for the implementation of the project content. 5. Building a system of methodological work to support the professional activities of teachers participating in the project. 6. Description of the conditions for managerial assistance to teachers in the dissemination of positive experience (writing a scientific article for publication in the conference proceedings, designing the author's program)

Educational significance of the project	The implementation of the project will ensure the solution of the tasks of the Federal State Budget BEFORE: combining education and upbringing into a holistic educational process based on spiritual , moral and socio-cultural values and socially accepted rules and norms of behavior in the interests of a person, family, society (respect for adult work, understanding of the value of work, interest in various adult professions); achieving targets: the child has a positive attitude to different types of work.
Technology and scale - The project can be used both in the system of additional education of preschool children	The project can be used both in the system of additional education of preschool children age predictability, and can be included in the content of the main educational programs of the preschool educational institution in the content of educational areas: "cognitive development", "social and communicative development", "speech development"
Project resource support	As the normative basis of the project, the Regulation on the innovative activity of preschool teachers, the Regulation on the creative group for the development of the project is determined. Inclusion of the content of projects (as modules) in an additional general educational general development program. The scientific and methodological basis is the program and the content of the project modules. Staffing – teachers of preschool educational institutions, participants of the integrated project. As information and material and technical resources, computer classes of preschool institutions, lego-designing classrooms, experimental laboratories equipped in group rooms corners of the machine-building plant workshop

Conclusions. As a result of this study, various aspects of early career guidance were studied when using game formats that can positively influence the choice of a future career. Also, as a result, it was possible to study the influence of games on the development of skills and competencies necessary for their future professional activity in older preschool children. The work investigated the tools of pedagogical design in early career guidance, the use of projects, augmented reality and artificial intelligence systems, as well as the game "MeTycoon" as innovative methods that are useful for older preschool children for self-determination. The study managed to study the main aspects of the periodization of career guidance for Ginsberg, as well as to highlight the earliest period of children's professional orientation "fantasy". The paper presents the tools of early career guidance, which have a positive impact on the future professional self-determination of the child. In this paper, the pedagogical design tool "Laptop" is studied, as well as its main tasks and functions in career guidance work with older preschool children. Researchers who will study the issues of pedagogical design in the early professional orientation of older preschool children are recommended to pay special attention to the field of digital models of career guidance work.

References:

1. Batyshev S.Ya. Professional pedagogy / S.Ya. Batyshev. – M.: Vocational education, 1997.
2. Bepalko V.P. Pedagogy and progressive learning technologies / V.P. Bepalko. – M., 1995.
3. Clarin M. V. Innovations in world pedagogy / M.V. Clarin. – Riga: Experiment, 1998.
4. Likhachev B.T. Pedagogy. Course of lectures / B.T. Likhachev. – 4th ed., reprint. and dop. – M.: Yur-ayt-M, 2001.
5. Parola, A., Di Fuccio, R., Marcionetti, J. & Limone, P. 2023. Digital games for career guidance: a systematic review using PRISMA guidelines. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 1, 1-11.
6. Batubar, J., 2013. Career Development and Selection According to Ginzberg and Its Implications for Guidance and Counseling. *Journal of Counseling and Education*, 1 (1), 43-47.
7. Dudi, G. 2012. Career Development Guidance Model (Study of Development of a Career Development Guidance Model for Deaf Students in SLB-B Bandung). *Educational Research Journal*, 13 (2), 1-12.
8. Savickas, M. 2019. Career counseling. Washington: American Psychological Association.
9. Muslihati, M., Hambali, I.M., Zen, E.F. & Apriani, R. 2021. Pelatihan Implementasi Bimbingan Karier Berbasis Four C's dan HOTs Bagi Guru BK

SMK Se-Kota Malang. *Suluh Bendang: Jurnal Ilmiah Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat*, 21 (3), 178-185.

10. Аманбаева, Э.А., Жаксылыкова, Н.Е. & Кенбаева, Г.К. 2019. Выбор профессии-основа профориентационной работы. *Методологические проблемы современной педагогики и образования*, 2 (62), 371-375.

11. Meluso, A., Zheng, M., Spires, H.A. & Lester, J. 2012. Enhancing 5th graders' science content knowledge and self-efficacy through game-based learning. *Computers & Education*, 59 (2), 497-504.

12. Dunwell, I., Lameris, P. de Freitas, S., Petridis, P., Star, K., Hendrix, M. & Arnab, S. 2013. *MeTycoon: A game-based approach to career guidance*. 5th International Conference on Games and Virtual Worlds for Serious Applications (VS-GAMES) (1-5). Poole: IEEE.

13. Карий, И.И. & Фарафонова, Н.Н. 2021. Лэпбук как инновационная форма ранней профориентации детей дошкольного возраста. *Педагогическая наука и практика*, 4 (34), 117-120.

14. Park, H. J., & Lee, S. 2018. AR-based game for kindergarten children's career education. *Journal of Digital Convergence*, 16 (10), 233-241.

15. Dolhopolov, S., Honcharenko, T., Dolhopolova, S. A., Riabchun, O., Delembovskyi, M. & Omelianenko, O. 2022. Use of Artificial Intelligence Systems for Determining the Career Guidance of Future University Student. 2022 International Conference on Smart Information Systems and Technologies (SIST) (1-6). Nur-Sultan: IEEE.